

GENESIS OF IDEAS AND IMAGES IN "BIRD LANGUAGE" POEMS

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It is known that Allah, while adorning man, gave him a quality that is not found in other creatures - the ability to speak. What a blessing this is for us! With the help of the human language and with the speech created from the chain of thoughts formed in it, sometimes he leads himself to enlightenment, and sometimes to ignorance. Yes, although the tongue is actually a small thing, its prayer and rebellion are big. In a hadith narrated from Saeed bin Jubayr, may Allah bless him and grant him peace, the Messenger of Allah, may God bless him and grant him peace, says: "When a human child wakes up, all the members look at the tongue and say: "Fear Allah about us. Because if you are right, we will be right. If you are broken, we will also be broken, we will lose the Truth"¹.

The fact that the human language has its own power among the social creations of existence is expressed in the above hadith. It is known from history that every person who came to the earth with the status of Prophet was gifted by Allah the Most High with a special ability and a great wisdom that ordinary people are incapable of. This is what God Almighty taught Sulaiman, the possessor of such incomparable power of miracles, to speak the language of birds. About this, the following verse is stated in Surah "Naml" of the Holy Qur'an: "Sulaiman succeeded David (in prophethood and knowledge) and said: "O people, we have been shown the language of birds (and all animals) and (the prophet) and given to kings) of all things."²

In the history of Sufism literature, based on the "Bird's Tongue", the idea of reaching the beauty and grace of the divine love-Allah by making the human soul subservient not to the ego, was transferred to art. In verses 20-23 of Surah "Naml" of the Holy Qur'an, which we mentioned above, the Hudhud bird told the Prophet Solomon about the rule of a woman named Bilqis in the city of Saba' in the country of Yemen and the worship of the sun by the people under her command. conveys the message. Through this verse, it is explained that the inhabitants of a country of Hudhud became Muslims. In the epic "Mantiq ut-Tayr" by Sheikh Fariduddin Attar, who captivated the incomparable wordsmith Alisher Navoi as a child, the following verses refer to the 16th verse of Surah "Naml", that is, the science of the "language of birds" was taught to the Prophet Suleiman. refers to:

"Qilcha berdi chumoliga, kamar

¹ Imam Ahmad Ghazali. Language disasters and ways to avoid them. -T.: MUNIR, 2021.-9 p.

² The Holy Qur'an. The author of the translation and comments is Alauddin Mansur. - T.: Cholpon, 2001. - 419 p.

Ul Sulaymon birla bo'ldi hamsamar.
Berdi xil'at unga, abbosiy tuni,
Bebadal "Tosin" ga esh etdi uni"³.

The word "Naml" comes from Arabic and means "ant", and it is also mentioned about the ant, one of the weakest and most laborious creatures of Allah, so the surah is named so. The first verse of this sura begins with "To sin".

Hazrat Navoi, who benefited from the divine inspiration of this epic, created a unique work called "Lison ut-tayr" in Turkish verse. In the following answer given by the hudhud bird in chapter LXXXV of the work, we can understand why the hudhud bird has special knowledge and intelligence among the birds of the world in both epics, which is reflected in the incident related to the Prophet Solomon in the Holy Qur'an.

"O'truda bu bo'ldi Hudhudning so'zi:

"Kim manga tushmish Sulaymonning ko'zi.

Haq taolokim anga aylab nazar,
Ham rasul aylab edi, ham tojvar.

Jinnu insu vahshu tayr ustida shoh-

Aylab erdi oni lutf aylab iloh.
Bo'yla sohibdavlati sohbarsarvi-
Iltifotin topti men yanglig' haqir.

Ondin o'ldi bu qadar izzat manga,

Bosh uza bu afsari rif'at manga.
Kimga-kim aylar nazar ahli safo,
Ul nazar tufrog'ni aylar kimyo."⁴

With the wisdom of this knowledge, Hudhud answers every question with wisdom and precision during the journeys of the birds of the world in search of Simurg. In fact, Hudhud is among the creations whose name is mentioned in the Holy Qur'an.

If we admit, we can come to the reasonable opinion that the Holy Qur'an serves as the main source for the creation of epics in the "Language of the Bird" series. As the first example of "Kushnama", when we analyze the "Tayr story" of the encyclopedist Abu Ali Ibn Sina, in this work, the birds of the world fly to the presence of the perfect King in search of justice and truth for themselves. We can see the same conclusion in Risolat ut-Tayr. Although each of the four spiritual-educational works of the "Bird Language" series listed above differ in terms of the period of creation, size, and author, the main idea is to show the love of God in ourselves, in our soul, through figurative images-birds. means that the common trials and tests that a person faces on the way to this great goal are aimed at understanding that it is from God. Therefore, as a conclusion, it is not wrong to say that based on the images and ideas presented in "Kushnama", the holy book - the verses of the Holy Qur'an is an important source.

³ Sheikh Fariduddin Attar. Logic ut-tyre. -T.: New age generation, 2022. -15 p.

⁴ Alisher Navoi. Lison ut-tyre. - T.: Gafur Ghulam publishing house, 2019. -132 p.

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